

Synthesis of linear tetrapeptide : Ile-Ala-Leu-Leu with potent anthelmintic activity

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Abstract : Amino acids are biologically active organic compounds that combine together to form peptides and proteins. Peptides can have various important functions such as antioxidant, anthelmintic, antiinsecticidal activity etc. A novel linear tetrapeptide L-(Ile-Ala-Leu-Leu) was synthesized using 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide (EDC) by solution phase peptide synthesis. The compound was characterized by ^1H NMR. The compound was tested for different biological activities i.e. antioxidant and anthelmintic activity. The tetrapeptide showed poor antioxidant activity compared to standard ascorbic acid and potent anthelmintic activity compared to standard Mebendazole tablets.

Keywords : Tetrapeptide, ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide, antioxidant activity, anthelmintic activity.

Introduction

Amino acids are biologically active organic compounds that combine together to form proteins. Two amino acids can be coupled together to form a dipeptide. The dipeptides can be further coupled to form tripeptides, tetrapeptides, pentapeptide etc. Peptides can function as enzymes, hormones, growth promoters or inhibitors, immunomodulators, enzyme inhibitors or substrates and neurotransmitters^{1,2}. In many of the past literatures, they have reported about tetrapeptides, hexapeptides etc. which have shown moderate anthelmintic activity³⁻⁶. A novel tetrapeptide with the sequence Ile-Ala-Leu-Leu was synthesized by solution phase peptide synthesis and was characterized by ^1H NMR. The first amino acid was protected at the amino end using tertiary butyloxy carbonyl group whereas the second amino acid was protected at the carboxyl by esterification. The protected amino acids were coupled together using coupling reagent EDC. Using the same procedure another dipeptide was synthesized. Then the amino group of one dipeptide and carboxyl group of another dipeptide was deprotected and both the dipeptides were coupled together to form the desired tetrapeptide⁷.

The synthesized tetrapeptide was tested for antioxidant activity by following DPPH method and anthelm-

intic activity was carried out following Garg's method. The standard used for antioxidant activity was ascorbic acid and Mebendazole was taken as the standard drug for anthelmintic activity. The results showed that the tetrapeptide exhibited poor antioxidant activity but potent anthelmintic activity.

Experimental

Commercially available reagents and analytical grade solvents were used without further purification. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used to dry the compounds. All amino acids, Boc, EDC, trifluoroacetic acid, tetrahydrofuran, lithium hydroxide, anhydrous sodium sulphate and sodium bicarbonate were obtained from Avra Chemicals. Methanol and isopropanol were obtained from Rankem and chloroform was obtained from Nice Chemicals. Boc amino acids, amino acid methylester hydrochlorides and dipeptides were synthesized using standard procedures. Biological evaluation of the synthesized compound was also carried out using standard procedures. FTIR spectrometer was used to record IR spectra. The values were reported as ν_{max} (cm^{-1}). ^1H NMR Bruker JEOL (400 MHz) NMR spectrometer was used to record ^1H NMR spectra using CDCl_3 as solvent. The chemical shift values are reported in ppm relative to TMS ($\delta = 0$) as internal standard.

Synthesis of dipeptides :

The carboxyl protected amino acid (L-alanine methyl ester, L-leucine methyl ester) (10 mmol) was dissolved in CHCl_3 (15 ml). Triethylamine (4 ml) was added at 0°C to the above mixture and stirred for 15 min. The amino protected amino acids (Boc-L-isoleucine, Boc-L-leucine) (10 mmol) in CHCl_3 (15 ml) and 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide (EDC) (1.9 g, 10 mmol) were added while stirring. The reaction mixture was filtered after 12 h. The filtrate was washed with 5% NaHCO_3 (20 ml), 5% HCl (20 ml) and water (20 ml). Anhydrous Na_2SO_4 was used to dry the organic layer. The product obtained was recrystallized from chloroform and petro-

leum ether ($40\text{--}60^\circ$).

Synthesis of linear tetrapeptide :

The amino group of one dipeptide and the carboxyl group of another dipeptide were deprotected. The deprotected dipeptides were coupled following similar procedure to that of dipeptide. By using this method Boc-Ile-Ala-Leu-Leu-OMe, tetrapeptide was synthesized. Finally the boc and ester group were removed to obtain the desired tetrapeptide i.e. Ile-Ala-Leu-Leu.

Antioxidant activity :

The antioxidant activity of the tetrapeptide Ile-Ala-Leu-Leu was carried out by DPPH method, described by

(i) Coupling – EDC, CH_3Cl , Et_3N , 12 h stirring, (ii) Ester deprotection – $\text{THF} : \text{H}_2\text{O}$, LiOH , 1 h stirring, (iii) Boc deprotection – TFA , CH_3Cl , 1.5 h stirring.

Scheme

Ilham Gulcin *et al.*⁸⁻¹¹. A standard solution of 0.1 M DPPH solution was prepared. The stock solutions of 100 ppm concentration of ascorbic acid and the synthesized tetrapeptide were prepared. From these stock solutions, solution of 50 ppm and 25 ppm were prepared. From each concentration 3 ml solution was transferred to a test tube and 1 ml of DPPH was added to this. A blank solution was prepared by adding 3 ml methanol and 1 ml DPPH. Then the test tubes were kept in the dark for 30 min. Then the absorbance was measured at 517 nm using UV spectrophotometer. The ascorbic acid acts as a standard and the antioxidant activity was calculated by the following equation :

$$\text{DPPH scavenging activity (\%)} = (A_c - A_s/A_c) \times 100$$

where, A_c represents control absorbance and A_s represents sample absorbance.

Anthelmintic activity :

Anthelmintic activity of the synthesized tetrapeptide was carried out following Garg's method^{12,13}. The sample was stirred with 15% Tween 80 triturated with water for 30 min to obtain a suspension. The tetrapeptide sample and the standard sample (Mebendazole) were prepared at a concentration of 100 mg in 50 ml Tween 80. A control suspension of 15% Tween 80 in 50 ml distilled water was also taken. *Eudrilus eugeniae* (earthworms) were added to each, standard, sample and control and the paralyzing time and death time was noted. The earthworms were placed in warm water (50 °C) to confirm the death time.

Results and discussion

The compound L-(Ile-Ala-Leu-Leu) was synthesized using EDC as coupling reagent by solution phase peptide synthesis. The compound was obtained in moderate yield. Table 1 shows the physical data of the tetrapeptide L-(Ile-Ala-Leu-Leu).

Table 1. Physical data of the compound

Sr. No.	Compd.	Physical state	% Yield
1.	L-(Ile-Ala-Leu-Leu)	Semi-solid	62.8

Spectral analysis :

¹H NMR : 6.7 (NH, d), 2.01 (NH₂), 0.96 (CH₃, d), 1.07 (CH₃, d), 1.48 (CH₃, d), 1.03 (CH₃, d), 3.68 (OCH₃),

1.22 (CH₂, t), 1.75 (CH₂, t), 1.73 (CH₂, t), 2.15 (CH, m), 3.55 (CH, m), 4.98 (CH, m), 4.57 (CH, m), 1.83 (CH, m), 4.36 (CH, m); IR : 3446.79 (amide N-H), 1691.57 (amide C=O), 1736 (ester C=O), 1020-1047 cm⁻¹ (ester C-O); Mass : The molecular ion peak was obtained at 540.9.

Antioxidant activity :

The synthesized compound was tested for antioxidant activity following DPPH method. Ascorbic acid showed better results as compared to the tetrapeptide L-(Ile-Ala-Leu-Leu), which showed poor results. The antioxidant activity results are tabulated in Table 2.

Table 2. Antioxidant activity results

Sr. no.	Sample	Concentration	Absorbance	% Inhibition
1.	Blank		0.518	
2.	Ascorbic acid	25	0.160	69.11
		50	0.157	69.69
		100	0.155	70.07
3.	L-(Ile-Ala-Leu-Leu)	25	0.389	24.90
		50	0.386	25.48
		100	0.382	26.25

Anthelmintic activity :

The synthesized compound showed potent anthelmintic activity as compared to Mebendazole which was taken as the standard drug. The anthelmintic activity results are tabulated in Table 3.

Table 3. Anthelmintic activity results

Sr. no.	Sample	Concentration (mg)	Paralysing time (h : min)	Death time (h : min)
1.	Control	-		
2.	Mebendazole	100	3 : 05	3 : 40
3.	L-(Ile-Ala-Leu-Leu)	100	2 : 28	2 : 47

Conclusion

The tetrapeptide was conveniently synthesized by solution phase technique using EDC (coupling reagent). The compound was synthesized in moderate yield and in a pure form. The synthesized tetrapeptide was characterized by IR and ¹H NMR. The compound exhibited poor antioxidant activity and potent anthelmintic activity.

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